

THE ENERGY-ABSORBING CHARACTERISTICS OF COMPOSITE-REINFORCED HONEYCOMBS

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ABSTRACT

The energy-absorbing characteristics of aluminium honeycomb reinforced with CFRP tubes subjected to quasi-static compressive loading is studied herein. Crushing tests on individual CFRP tubes yielded specific energy absorption values as high as 110 kJ/kg. It was observed that the composite tubes efficiently absorbed large amounts of energy via a number of failure modes, similar to those observed in much larger tubes. Following this, between one and nine composite tubes were inserted into square blocks of aluminium honeycomb. Subsequent crushing tests on these tube-reinforced honeycomb structures resulted in SEA values of up to 100 kJ/kg. This evidence suggests that tube-reinforced honeycombs offer significant potential for use in energy-absorbing structures.

1 INTRODUCTION

The outstanding energy-absorbing characteristics of composite tubes have long been recognized and exploited by the engineering sector [1–4]. Comprehensive experimental investigations on numerous types of cylindrical structure have revealed that composite materials offer superior specific energy absorption values over metallic structures [4–6]. Previous work has shown that specific energy absorption values for composite tubes often exceed 100 kJ/kg, with the value increasing rapidly as the ratio of the tube diameter to the wall thickness (D/t) is decreased [3]. In terms of the crushing modes of composite tubes, four far more complex mechanisms than those of the conventional materials were reported by Farley and Jones [7]. The failure mechanisms include a fragmentation mode, a splaying mode, a brittle fracturing and progressive folding. Their findings indicate that the resulted crushing length is a qualitative measure that is related to the crushing efficiency. In this context, an understanding in controlling these crushing mechanisms allows one to maximise the specific energy absorption characteristics of composite tubes.

In addition to these composite tubes, honeycomb structures are also widely used as an excellent energy absorber in various industrial applications. In contrast to these composite tubes, out-of-plane compression tests on aluminium honeycomb cores offer values of SEA lying between 9 and 45 kJ/kg. Other cores such as Nomex and polymeric foams yielded lower values of specific energy absorption up to 13 kJ/kg and 17 kJ/kg, respectively [8]. An extensive experimental and numerical investigation has been conducted by Ivanez et al. [9] to study the characteristics of the energy absorption capability of aluminium honeycomb cores under lateral crushing loads. It was found that out-of-plane compression of aluminium honeycomb exhibits folds along the cell walls, which developed oscillations at the plateau stage in the load-displacement curve. The strength is generally independent of the height of the honeycomb cells but greatly influenced by the material density [10].

There are numerous studies [11–14] that focus on the possibility of enhancing the energy absorbing capacity of core materials. Vaidya et al. [12] fabricated reinforced foam cores by embedding titanium, pultruded glass/epoxy rods and steel Z-pins in foam panels. They reported that the buckling of the pins resulted in a higher transverse stiffness value compared to unreinforced foam. In order to further enhance the energy absorption capacity of metal tube reinforced foams, Karagiozova et al. [13]

modelled the efficiency of the reinforcing system under quasi-static loading. It was found that the foam/tube strength ratio determined the increase in the force per unit area of system. Found et al. [14] studied experimentally the energy absorption properties of a polyurethane foam sandwich panel with four fibre-reinforced plastic tubular inserts subjected to quasi-static compression loading. The results showed that by ensuring progressive brittle failure mechanism of the structure, higher specific energy absorption values were achieved.

One option for dramatically increasing these values for such core materials is to embed small diameter composite tubes into cells in the honeycomb, thereby exploiting the supporting ability of the core and the low D/t values of the tubes. The aim of the current work is to investigate the crushing characteristics of tube-reinforced cores, with a view to developing a highly efficient energy-absorbing system. Initially, compression tests were undertaken to focus on understanding the energy-absorbing response of plain composite tube arrays, which serve as comparison purpose. Then, quasi-static tests were conducted on the honeycomb-reinforced with the composite tube to investigate the energy-absorbing characteristics. Finally, conclusions were drawn based on the deformation and specific energy absorption results reported herein.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The cores studied here were manufactured from an aluminum honeycomb from the Hexcel Corporation and carbon fibre reinforced plastic tubes from Easy Composites Ltd. The former was supplied in 20 mm thick sheets with a cell size of 6.35 mm and a density of 37 kg/m^3 . Square 45 x 45 mm coupons were removed from the honeycomb layers using a bandsaw. The CFRP tubes tested here were prepared using a roll-wrapping technique with an outer diameter, D_o , equal to 6 mm, an internal diameter, D , of 4 mm, giving tubes with $D/t = 4$. A 45° chamfer at one end of the composite tube was introduced to serve as a trigger during crushing.

Initial tests were undertaken to evaluate the crushing characteristics of the individual tubes. A 50 mm height aluminium block fixture consisting of nine holes in a three by three array was manufactured. Each hole in the aluminium block has a diameter of 4.08 mm and an approximate depth of 50 mm. In Figure 1(a), a 4 mm diameter steel rod, 30 mm long was inserted into a hole in the block. The 20 mm long composite tubes were then positioned as shown in Figure 1(b).

The reinforced cores were prepared by inserting the tubes into the cells in the honeycomb. The number of tubes inserted into each sample was varied between one and nine, as shown in Figure 1(c). Each of the specimens was crushed at a constant crosshead speed of 10 mm/minute using a Universal Testing Machine Instron 5969 with a 50 kN load cell. The specific energy absorption (SEA) of each structure was calculated from the area under the load-displacement trace normalised by the mass of the CFRP tubes.

Figure 1. The top view of the aluminium block rig for individual tubes testing with five (a) steel rods inserted into holes and (b) composite tubes positioned prior to testing. (c) An untested reinforced core sample with 7 tubes.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presented the results of the individual composite tube and reinforced core tested under quasi-static compression. The load-displacement histories, crushing characteristics, and the corresponding failure mechanism series are discussed. Table 1 lists the areal density, mass and

measured specified energy absorption of the individual tube and reinforced honeycomb.

No of tube	Areal density (%)	Mass tube (g)	Mass tube + honeycomb (g)	SEA tube (kJ/kg)	SEA tube + honeycomb (kJ/kg)
0	0.00	-	1.7	-	14.5
1	2.38	0.43	2.1	111.2	42.9
2	4.76	0.86	2.6	105.3	54.1
3	7.14	1.29	3	110.5	63.2
4	9.52	1.72	3.6	115.1	69.5
5	11.90	2.15	4.1	107.1	83.8
6	14.29	2.58	4.6	112.5	87.7
7	16.67	3.01	5.1	112.2	88.6
8	19.05	3.44	5.7	110.6	97.9
9	21.43	3.87	6.1	107.6	99.9

Table 1: Details of the reinforced honeycomb.

3.1 Tests on Individual Tubes

Figure 2(a) shows typical force-displacement traces following tests on samples based on 3 to 9 tubes. In all cases, the traces displayed similar trends, with the force increasing linearly to a maximum whose magnitude obviously depends on the number of tubes. Following the initial peak in the trace, the force decreases steadily up to a point where the force increases rapidly due to densification of the tubes between the steel plates of the test machine.

Figure 2: (a) Typical force-displacement traces associated with crush tests on the tube reinforced aluminium honeycombs and (b) comparison of the SEA values between the individual tube and reinforced core structures.

The SEA values of the individual tube ranging between 105 to 112 kJ/kg were plotted in Figure 2(b). The SEA values from tests on the individual tubes averaging approximately 110 kJ/kg. It is interesting to note that there is no significant effect on the SEA values as the number of tubes was increased from 1 to 9.

Figures 3(a) and (b) show a single and nine composite tubes during the crushing process. Closer

inspection of the crushed samples indicated that the CFRP tubes failed in progressive failure modes by splaying and forming small fragments. This suggests that the tubes absorbed significant amount of energy during the crushing process. Here, a similar failure mechanism was observed in the single and multiple tubes. Figures 3(c) and (d) show the resulting photographs of a single tube and nine tubes following compression tests. It was observed that both samples crushed by producing significant amounts of fibre fracture and splaying.

Figure 3: (a) a single tube and (b) nine tubes undergoing crushing. Crushed sample of (c) a single tube and (d) nine tubes.

3.2 Tests on Reinforced Cores

The study investigated the specific energy absorption of the composite tubes embedded in aluminium honeycomb structures. Figure 4 shows typical force-displacement traces following crush tests on the three to nine tubes-reinforced aluminium honeycombs. All traces exhibit similar characteristics, with force increasing to a maximum and failure continued in a stable manner forming plateau force from 13 kN to 35 kN for the number of tubes tested. The plateau region indicates that the structure is absorbing energy by combination of progressive failure modes of the CFRP tubes and the folding of aluminium cell walls as the displacement increases. As the crushing continues, the load drops slightly before increases rapidly due to densification of the structure.

By comparing to the curves in Figure 2(a), it was observed that the response of the embedded CFRP tubes is superior to the individual tubes due to higher levels of support provided by the honeycomb. Photographs of crushed samples containing 1 and 9 CFRP tubes embedded in aluminium honeycombs are shown in Figure 5(a) and (b), respectively. An interesting phenomenon observed in the photographs was that all of the tubes crushed in similar failure modes, involving splaying and interaction between neighbouring tubes during the crushing process. Given that the honeycomb served to support the collapse of the tubes in a controlled manner, there is an absence of the well-defined cell wall wrinkling as observed during tests on plain honeycomb specimens.

Figure 4: Typical force-displacement traces following crush tests on the tubes-reinforced aluminium honeycombs.

Figure 5: Photographs of crushed (a) four and (b) nine cell samples.

It can be seen in Figure 2(b), that the specific energy absorption varies from 63 to 100 kJ/kg for the three to nine samples respectively, suggesting that increasing the number of CFRP tubes in the 45 x 45 mm honeycomb structures has a great influence on the energy-absorbing capability. It is worth mentioning that the specific energy absorption value of the nine tube-reinforced core approaches the value for the tubular array with nine tubes. Evidently, combining composite tubes with aluminium honeycomb has shown that values of specific energy absorption as high as 100 kJ/kg can be achieved.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The axial crushing performance of CFRP tubes-reinforced aluminium honeycombs has been studied at quasi-static rates of strain. Initial attention focuses on the energy-absorbing response and crushing mechanism of individual composite tube. In general, it was shown that the SEA values did not vary greatly as the number of tubes was increased from 1 to 9, with specific energy absorption values ranging between 105 to 112 kJ/kg. The energy absorption capability is dependent on the crushing modes, in this case involving splaying and fibre fracture. CFRP tubes-reinforced aluminium honeycomb structures have been developed in which one to nine tubes are embedded in aluminium honeycombs. It has been shown that these structures offer attractive specific energy absorption values, with values up to 100 kJ/kg has been achieved. The mechanism underlying the enhancement is attributed to the higher levels of support provided by the honeycomb to the tubes during the crushing process. Hence, this evidence shows that composite tube-reinforced aluminium honeycombs do offer great potential as lightweight structural materials for use in energy absorbing applications.

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